

Deep Kernel Learning for Operational Limits of Autonomous Surface Vessels

Nate Clemett^{1,*} and Matthew Collette¹

¹ University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI, USA

Abstract. Autonomous surface vessels require predictive models that remain reliable across routine and extreme sea states. However, many existing models generalize poorly outside the training domain. This study applies deep kernel learning, which couples a neural network feature extractor with a Gaussian process, to predict Root-Mean-Square (RMS) heave and pitch motions from vessel and environmental inputs while quantifying predictive uncertainty. The resulting predictive distributions are translated into task specific operational limits by computing the probability that motions remain below prescribed thresholds as a function of significant wave height for each heading and speed. A joint survivability metric aggregates the motion constraints and yields a 90 percent survivability contour that defines a conservative operational envelope for route planning. Demonstrations with a simulated autonomous surface vessel trained on a hindcast weather dataset show that the proposed framework achieves accurate motion prediction in routine sea states while providing calibrated uncertainty estimates in hazardous conditions. These uncertainty measures enable risk-aware decision making by distinguishing between regions of confident prediction and regions requiring caution. Because the model structure allows rapid updating as new data are acquired, the framework supports continual refinement of operational envelopes and establishes a principled foundation for defining and adapting safe operating limits for autonomous vessel.

Key words: *deep kernel learning, limit-state uncertainty, seakeeping, operational envelope*

1. Introduction

The adoption of autonomous surface vessels for extended missions in commercial and defense applications is accelerating. The removal of onboard human judgment increases reliance on predictive models to maintain safety across variable ocean conditions. Experience from long duration trials has shown that machinery failures, structural fatigue, and unexpected sea states can force intervention or premature mission termination, which motivates formal definition of operational limits before deployment.

In crewed operations, mariners compensate for uncertainty with conservative decision rules. Comparable behavior in autonomous systems requires models that deliver accurate predictions together with calibrated measures of confidence. Closed-form seakeeping methods and physics based hydrodynamic models provide useful baselines but may not capture nonlinear responses in heavy seas. Purely data driven models can achieve high accuracy within the training domain yet often become overconfident when extrapolating to unobserved or hazardous conditions. These limitations motivate probabilistic approaches that learn complex relationships while quantifying uncertainty.

Deep kernel learning addresses this need by coupling a neural network feature extractor with a Gaussian process. The network learns a nonlinear representation of vessel and environmental inputs, and the Gaussian process yields a Bayesian predictive distribution for motion responses. In this study the framework is used to predict root mean square heave and pitch from significant wave height, wave period, relative heading, and vessel speed while producing uncertainty estimates suitable for safety critical decision making.

This framework predicts motion RMS values of an autonomous surface vessel using hindcast weather data, while quantifying uncertainty in those predictions. The resulting probabilistic outputs are directly

*Correspondence to: nclemett@umich.edu

translated into task-specific operational limits by estimating the likelihood that motions remain within prescribed thresholds across headings and speeds. These limits are then combined into a joint survivability metric, producing a conservative operational envelope defined by a ninety percent survivability contour. This envelope provides a principled foundation for safe route planning and risk-informed decision making in variable and extreme sea states.

2. Background

2.1. Literature Review

To examine the challenges associated with extended deployments of complex autonomous vessels, Collette et al. [7] carried out a research program that combined crew interviews, vessel reviews, simulation, and STPA analysis to identify critical areas for further study. The interviews highlighted the dependence of operators on accumulated experience and on communication with both onboard personnel and shore-based support for planning medium to long-term missions. These communication practices were typically informal and varied considerably across vessels, which presents difficulties in reproducing equivalent monitoring and planning in autonomous systems. In the absence of experienced crew, an autonomous surface vessel must be capable of adapting and improving throughout its operational life in order to achieve performance levels comparable to those of crewed ships.

Several recent attempts at long-duration missions with autonomous ships have encountered difficulties that required human intervention. The United States Navy's *Sea Hunter*, a 132-foot unmanned surface vessel, attempted a transit from San Diego to Pearl Harbor. During the voyage, mechanical failures in the engine and generator necessitated boarding on three separate occasions before the vessel reached Hawaii [8]. Similarly, the IBM *Mayflower*, a 15-meter ship designed for transatlantic crossings, faced significant challenges. Its first attempt ended near Portugal after a generator fracture caused a breakdown and a diesel spill. Following repairs, a second attempt was made, but additional generator malfunctions forced the vessel to stop in the Azores, after which the mission was shortened to conclude in Halifax, Nova Scotia [11]. Although these failures were primarily mechanical, they underscore the importance of clearly defining and understanding operational limits for autonomous platforms prior to undertaking extended missions.

When structural damage is identified in vessels, operational restrictions are often imposed to prevent further degradation, and in severe cases the vessel may be retired from service. Several Littoral Combat Ships (LCS) developed structural defects that resulted in hull cracking. To mitigate the progression of fatigue damage, these ships were limited to speeds below 20 knots in sea states exceeding 8 feet. This restriction significantly reduced their effectiveness and contributed to their decommissioning well before the anticipated end of service life [17].

Fjørtoft et al. [9] presented a Bayesian Network framework for rapid onboard assessment of grounding damage in ships. The approach integrates real-time sensor measurements, inspection data, and probabilistic models to estimate the extent of hull damage and evaluate survivability. By continuously updating as new information becomes available, the framework enables immediate adjustments to the vessel's safe operational envelope and supports risk-informed decision-making during emergency situations.

Page et al. [12] proposed a simulation-based approach to define and adapt safe operational envelopes for autonomous unmanned aerial systems (UAS) in offshore inspections. Drawing inspiration from manned Ship-Helicopter Operating Limits (SHOL) procedures, the method applies performance-based cost functions to determine when and why system components fail under varying wind conditions. This framework enables dynamic contraction of the operational envelope in response to subsystem degradation, providing a tool for risk-informed mission planning and autonomy assurance.

For an autonomous surface vessel (ASV) to operate reliably, both robust sensors and accurate machine learning models are essential for interpreting data and generating predictions. A variety of methods have been applied to forecast vessel motions. Schirmann et al. [2] developed predictive models using machine learning techniques with wave-model parameters as inputs. Ridge regression and neural network models were trained on multidirectional wave parameters and validated with ship data spanning more than 13,500 thirty-minute windows. Incorporating computationally efficient physics-based model predictions (PBMPs) as additional inputs substantially reduced motion amplitude mean-squared error (MSE). Furthermore, test-

ing on data from a sister vessel confirmed the adaptability of the models. These findings highlight the value of combining physics-based information with data-driven approaches to improve prediction accuracy

To support the determination of operational conditions, Cetin et al. [6] applied closed-form solutions developed by Jorgen Jensen to predict wave-induced vessel responses using response amplitude operators (RAOs). Leveraging weather forecasts, they produced short- and medium-term predictions of RAOs for a pipe-laying vessel, where loading conditions varied continuously due to the nature of its operations. Similarly, Petranovic et al. [13] employed Jensen’s closed-form solutions to estimate extreme wave loads using a hindcast wave database. Their approach enabled prediction of short- and long-term extreme bending moments, with a Gumbel distribution fitted to the annual extreme values.

This work uses multiple degrees of freedom, specifically heave and pitch, to create an envelope for sea-keeping. Due to the inaccuracy of pre-deployment models, the ASV’s envelope is shown to be inaccurate at launch. As a result, a way to rapidly update the envelope ensuring the vessel does not venture into dangerous seas is paramount.

Deep Kernel Learning (DKL) merges GPs with deep neural networks to overcome another limitation of classical GPs: the lack of automatic feature learning. Originally, GPs rely on user-defined kernels (e.g. RBF, Matern) on the raw inputs, which can struggle with complex high-dimensional data like images or with multiple interacting inputs. DKL addresses this by using a neural network to learn a representation on which a GP kernel is applied. The work by Wilson et al. [16] introduced this concept, showing that training a deep neural network and a GP end-to-end is possible by maximizing the GP marginal likelihood. In their formulation, the neural network acts as an input-dependent basis for the kernel. They demonstrated scalable deep kernel learning on large datasets up to two million samples by combining inducing point methods, kernel interpolation techniques, and exploiting structure in kernel matrices. The results showed improved accuracy over standalone deep networks and over standard GPs with hand-crafted kernels, validating that the combination leverages the strengths of both approaches.

Tighineanu et al. [15] introduced ScaML-GP, a scalable meta-learning framework based on Gaussian Processes designed for efficient learning across multiple tasks. The method employs a modular multi-task kernel that combines individual task posteriors into a joint Bayesian prior, enabling well-calibrated uncertainty estimates while maintaining linear scalability in the number of tasks. By conditioning on meta-data, ScaML-GP rapidly adapts to new tasks in the low-data regime and consistently outperforms existing meta-learning baselines across synthetic benchmarks and hyperparameter optimization tasks. This approach highlights the advantages of structured probabilistic modeling for reliable task adaptation in data-scarce settings

2.2. Operational Envelopes

Without a human crew onboard, it is essential to identify the factors and conditions that limit unmanned vessels from safely performing tasks or completing transits. Operational envelopes provide a framework for visualizing these safety constraints by representing a collection of tasks bounded by internal and external conditions, as illustrated in Figure 1.. Such tasks may include launching aerial drones, conducting safe transit, or executing collision avoidance maneuvers. By assembling these overlapping and often interconnected envelopes, it becomes possible to determine the conditions under which tasks can be performed safely, as well as the most restrictive factor governing each task.

Rødseth et al. [14] expanded the operational envelope concept beyond fixed geographic boundaries to incorporate environmental, technical, and human–machine responsibility factors. Using unified modeling language (UML), they developed a modular framework that enables reusable approvals, allowing ships to operate across diverse scenarios without re-certification, provided that new operations remain within the defined state space.

The present work applies this concept to seakeeping by constructing an operational envelope based on multiple degrees of freedom, specifically heave and pitch. Because pre-deployment models are often inaccurate, the initial ASV envelope at launch may not represent actual conditions. Consequently, a method for rapidly updating the envelope is required to ensure that the vessel does not enter unsafe seas.

Figure 1.: An example collection of Operational Envelopes [9]

2.3. Deep Kernel Learning (DKL)

Deep Kernel Learning is a predictive machine learning model that combines a neural network feature extractor with a Gaussian Process regression model. The two-stage architecture is dependent on a first deep neural network $\phi(x)$ mapping the raw input x to a latent feature vector $h = \phi(x)$, and second a GP operating on h as its input. By jointly training ϕ and the GP, the system can learn both the feature representation and the GP hyperparameters together via a single objective.

2.3.1. Feature Extractor Network

The feature extractor implements a deep neural network to learn a nonlinear embedding of the input features optimized for the downstream GP. The learned feature extractor $\phi(x; w)$ feeds the GP layer with a stationary base kernel acting in feature space. It is important to note that the feature extractor network is trained jointly with the GP. All parameters are learned jointly by maximizing the GP objective, which back-propagates through both the kernel and the feature extractor.

2.3.2. Gaussian Process (GP)

Gaussian Processes (GPs) have long been a popular Bayesian approach for modeling complex systems due to their flexibility and principled uncertainty estimates. A GP defines a distribution over functions, and exact GP regression yields not only a mean prediction but also a variance for each input, making it attractive for safety-critical domains. The largest drawback of GPs is poor scalability: exact inference requires $\mathcal{O}(N^3)$ operations for N training points, which becomes impractical for large datasets. For a more thorough explanation than the overview below, see Wilson et al. [16].

Gaussian processes (GPs) provide a Bayesian nonparametric prior over functions. Let $\mathcal{D} = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ with inputs $X = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^n$, $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^D$, and scalar targets $y = (y(x_1), \dots, y(x_n))^T$. Assume a mean vector $\mu_i = \mu(x_i)$ and covariance matrix $(K_{X,X})_{i,j} = k_\gamma(x_i, x_j)$ with hyperparameters γ that parameterize the kernel k_γ . If $f(x)$ is a Gaussian process then the function values has a joint Gaussian distribution,

$$f(X) = [f(x_1), \dots, f(x_n)]^T$$

Figure 2.: Deep Kernel Learning features utilizes a deep kernel that maps D dimensional inputs x through L hidden layers. This is followed by a base GP kernel layer with hyperparameters θ [16].

The GP prior induces a joint Gaussian distribution over function values,

$$f(X) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_X, K_{X,X}), \quad (K_{X,X})_{ij} = k_\gamma(x_i, x_j), \quad (\mu_X)_i = \mu(x_i). \quad (1)$$

With additive independent and identically distributed Gaussian observation noise $y(x) | f(x) \sim \mathcal{N}(f(x), \sigma^2)$, the posterior predictive distribution at test inputs X_* is Gaussian:

$$\mathbb{E}[f_*] = \mu_{X_*} + K_{X_*,X} [K_{X,X} + \sigma^2 I]^{-1} y, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{cov}(f_*) = K_{X_*,X_*} - K_{X_*,X} [K_{X,X} + \sigma^2 I]^{-1} K_{X,X_*}, \quad (3)$$

where $K_{X_*,X}$ denotes the $n_* \times n$ matrix of covariances from the GP evaluated at X_* . The kernel, which is parameterized by γ , affects all of the covariance matrices.

A common stationary choice is the radial basis function (RBF) kernel which is used in this work. The lengthscale ℓ controls the rate at which correlations decay with Euclidean distance.

$$k_{\text{RBF}}(x, x') = \exp\left(\frac{-\|x - x'\|}{2\ell^2}\right), \quad (4)$$

Kernel hyperparameters γ and the noise variance σ^2 are learned by maximizing a cost function. This work uses the ELBO lower bound method, and is described in the next section on scalable GPs.

Forming the Cholesky factor of $K_{X,X} + \sigma^2 I$ requires $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ time and $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ storage. Given the factorization, predictive means cost $\mathcal{O}(n)$ per test point and predictive variances cost $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ per test point.

2.3.3. Scalable GPs

To handle the large size of the dataset and ensure tractability, we use a sparse variational GP approximation. We introduce M inducing points h_{z_m} $m = 1^M$ in the feature space and approximate the full GP

Figure 3.: Weather Data Collection Zone

with an inducing point variational distribution $q(f)$, as demonstrated by Hensman et al. [10]. The inducing inputs h_{z_m} are initialized to a subset or to random points in the latent space and treated as learnable parameters that are optimized during training. This approach greatly reduces computational complexity. Instead of $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ scaling for n training points, the complexity becomes $\mathcal{O}(nm^2)$ using m inducing points. Sparse GP methods have been shown to match the performance of full GPs with small m , while significantly cutting training cost [10].

To avoid the $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ cost of exact inference, we introduce m inducing inputs $Z = \{z_j\}_{j=1}^m$ in the feature space and their latent values $\mathbf{u} = f(Z)$. With a Gaussian variational posterior $q(\mathbf{u}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{S})$, the evidence lower bound used for training is

$$\log p(\mathbf{y}) \geq \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{E}_{q(f_i)}[\log p(y_i | f_i)] - \text{KL}[q(\mathbf{u}) \| p(\mathbf{u})] \quad (5)$$

which reduces the cost to $\mathcal{O}(nm^2)$ and learns both the inducing locations Z and the kernel and network parameters jointly by maximizing the bound. Intuitively, the inducing variables summarize the latent function, so the GP only needs to manipulate an $m \times m$ covariance rather than the full $n \times n$ matrix.

3. Methodology

3.1. Weather Data

For this study, a comprehensive dataset of hindcast weather data was obtained from the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) for the entire year of 2018. This dataset collection process is extended from the prior work by Clemett et al. [1]. The data collected includes significant wave height H_s , peak period T_p , prominent wave direction β , wind direction, and wind speed. The ECMWF model is a nonhydrostatic model with a spatial resolution of 14 km [3]. The geographic focus of the data collection was a rectangular area in the North Pacific, delineated by the coordinates $[(20.0, -175.0), (50.0, -150.0)]$ and presented as a striped region in Figure 3..

3.1.1. Root Mean Square Values of Motion

A Bretschneider wave energy density spectrum was used in this work (Eq 6). The Bretschneider wave energy density spectrum is generated for the prevailing weather and ship conditions.

Table 1.: Vessel Characteristics

Main Particular	Notation	Value
Length BTW Perpendiculars	L_{PP}	59.0 (m)
Max Waterline Breadth	B_0	8.910 (m)
Beam	B	10.0 (m)
Draft	T	2.25 (m)
Transverse Metacentric Height	GM_T	1.237 (m)
Block Coefficient	Cb	0.61

$$S_\zeta(\omega) = \frac{173H_s^2}{T_p^4} \omega_e^{-5} \exp\left\{\frac{-692}{T_p^4} \omega_e^{-4}\right\} \quad (6)$$

$$S_\Phi(\omega) = |\Phi(\omega)|^2 \cdot S_\zeta(\omega) \quad (7)$$

The area under the response curve is the variance (Eq 8).

$$m_0 = \int_0^\infty S_\Phi(\omega) d\omega \quad (8)$$

Lastly, the Root-Mean Square of the respective response is determined through the square root of the response's variance (Eq 9).

$$\Phi_{RMS} = \sqrt{m_0} \quad (9)$$

3.2. Simulated At-Sea Data

The virtual vessel used for this work is loosely based on the Navy Vanguard ASV. Vanguard is part of the Project Overlord Class of Navy unmanned surface vehicles and launched in 2024 [5]. The main particulars used in this work and relevant to Section 4.1., are displayed in Table 1..

To generate a machine learning time-domain dataset, DSA Ocean's ProteusDS Simulation Toolbox was used [4]. First, a hullform was generated in Rhinoceros3D using the Orca3d Hull-Wizard plugin. For incident waves, the Froude-Krylov force is the complex amplitude of the exciting force. This excitation force, or F_j^I , is dependent on the unit normal to the hull surface out of the fluid n_j , the incident wave potential ϕ_1 , and the original relative velocity U_0 . The relatively easy computation is done through integrating the known incident wave potential over the body surface (Eq 10).

$$F_j^I = -\rho \iint_S n_j \left(i\omega_e - U_0 \frac{d}{dx} \right) \phi_1 ds \quad (10)$$

After calculating radiation and diffraction terms and setting a wave spectrum to match a collected hind-cast weather data sample, 900 seconds of data was collected. After collecting this 15 minutes of simulated data, the RMS of the motions were calculated.

Although the time-domain simulation would generally behave, occasionally unrealistic behavior would occur that would result in extremely large motions and RMS values. To prevent this from worsening model performance, outlier data samples were removed if the pitch RMS value for the run was larger than 15 degrees.

3.3. Model Set Up and Scoring Metrics

The model features are significant wave height, wave period, ship velocity, and relative heading between the ship and incident wave. To improve performance, the relative heading was decomposed into *sine* and *cosine* components to prevent wraparound that occurs at $(360^\circ, 0^\circ)$. The same features are utilized to predict either pitch or heave RMS values.

Figure 4.: Vanguard ASV transiting in waves within the Proteus Simulation Toolbox

The residual between ground truth and averaged predictions is found for all test points.

$$d_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i \quad (11)$$

Compute Z-scores by normalizing residuals using the standard deviation of actual values σ_y .

$$\sigma_y = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (12)$$

$$\bar{y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \quad (13)$$

$$\mu_z = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |z_i| \quad (14)$$

For model architecture, the feature extractor neural network consisted of a simple fully connected three layer with 32 neurons per layer. The Gaussian Process uses a Gaussian Likelihood and Radial Basis Function for kernel. The model was trained in PyTorch using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001. An 80/20 split for training and validation was used.

4. Results

4.1. Few-Shot Learning of Unseen, Large-Scale Wave Events

To simulate a vessel gaining experience in routine weather before pushing its operational limits, a two stage transfer learning based approach was implemented. To start, the vessel gains experience training in routine weather conditions. This was determined with randomly selected wave samples within the weather file containing significant wave heights ranging from 0-3.5 meters. After training on 3000 training shots of this data, the vessel was exposed to a large wave dataset consisting of 750 shots of data with conditions of ($H_s > 3.5m$). Because the data was randomly selected in these conditions, there were more samples similar to the 3.5m significant wave height opposed to extreme events close to 10m.

The test conditions consist of wave conditions containing data samples with significant wave heights ranging from (0 - 10.0m). This test dataset is also used in the Operational Envelope section.

4.1.1. Heave RMS

The Heave base model was trained on 3000 shots of routine weather data ($H_s < 3.5m$) before being evaluated against the (0 - 10.0m) test dataset. The left subplot of Figure 5. shows tight clustering in the smaller wave conditions where it was trained in. Extrapolation into the large waves, shown in the higher

Figure 5.: The left subplot displays the model trained with 3000 shots of data with wave heights less than 3.5m. After fine-tuning the training with 750 shots of waves from (0 - 10.0m), the accuracy increases and its uncertainty in extreme wave predictions shrink.

RMS values results in the model over-predicting heave RMS values. The base DKL model generally predicts a 90% confidence bounds that encompass the true value.

After the best model was saved from the routine weather training, it was loaded and exposed to 750 shots of extreme wave conditions. This results in the extreme predictions being refined, and the overall standard deviation of the z-score is essentially halved.

Despite the improvement in extreme wave prediction, the model often under and over predicts. Because of this, training in the extreme wave regime leads the uncertainty to collapse. This risks the vessel potentially sailing past its operational limit, overconfident that it is safe due to the small uncertainty band of the model.

Predictions in the small wave and low RMS region of the plot become worse due to model forgetfulness. This phenomena, and a remedy are explored in the past work Clemett et al. [1].

4.1.2. Pitch RMS

Because pitch has a large dependence on heading in heavy seas, it is a challenge to extrapolate pitch RMS motion when the model has only been trained in routine weather conditions.

This can be seen in Figure 6., where it accurately predicts pitch RMS motion in the domain where it was trained (small wave and RMS domain). Unlike Heave in Figure 5., the model severely overpredicts in extreme weather. Although the uncertainty estimate from the DKL model grows in this untrained test region, it does not expand enough to account for the poor accuracy in extreme conditions.

After 750 shots of extreme weather used for fine-tuning of the pitch model, prediction accuracy in the large-wave domain significantly increases. Despite this, the clustering of predictions is wider than in heave, with the model underpredicting and overpredicting in larger values. As a result, the overall accuracy for pitch is 36.7% worse than heave after large wave training.

4.2. Assembling the Operational Envelopes

Utilizing the predictions from the DKL trained models for pitch and heave, described in Sec 4.1., an Operational Envelope can be constructed to determine what heading, speed, and wave conditions are safe for a given task. To create the sea keeping envelope, the user provides an RMS limit for each degree of freedom for the task at hand. Depending on the task, this could vary widely. When it comes to critical safety of the vessel, heave is of less concern than other degrees of freedom and moments. However, for a task such as launching recovering a drone from the deck it may become increasingly important. By defining limits for each degree of freedom, the operational limits overlap and present a clear way to understand what headings and speeds are safe to operate in based on the weather. For this demonstration, a heave RMS limit

Figure 6.: The pitch model trained on routine weather is inadequate in extrapolating knowledge to extreme conditions (left). However, after 750 shots of extreme weather fine-tuning (right), the accuracy increases.

of 2.25 meters and pitch limit of 2.5 degrees were selected. These limits were arbitrarily chosen because they provide limit-states in rarer extreme weather, as well as overlapping with the other degree of freedom to showcase the Operational Envelope. For each of the colored polar subplots in Figure 7., the ground-truth limit-states from the ProteusDS time-domain simulations are presented by a black line. The predicted limit-states generated from the trained models is presented with a black dashed line.

To assemble the operational envelope dataset, weather samples were randomly selected until each bin of the polar plot contained five samples. Each bin spans 10 degrees representing ship heading and 0.45 meters along the radial axis representing significant wave heights that range from 1-10 meters. The bin color in the single degree of freedom polar plot is determined by a color map based on the RMS value of the bin and uses the mean of the five samples contained in each bin. It is important to note that the scale of the color map is different between pitch and heave. For this envelope, ship velocity was chosen to be 13 knots. For human crew to use the Operational Envelope as a visualization tool to analyze ASV limits, a collection of these envelopes at varying speeds may be used.

One complication that arises when assembling the operational envelope and the respective uncertainty measurements is to transfer uncertainty based knowledge in units of RMS motion to operational limits which is determined by significant wave height in meters.

At any given H_s , the predicted RMS is modeled as Gaussian,

$$R(H_s) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu(H_s), \sigma_R^2(H_s)). \quad (15)$$

The probability that this DOF remains within its limit L is

$$P_{\text{safe}}(H_s) = \Pr[R(H_s) \leq L] = \Phi\left(\frac{L - \mu(H_s)}{\sigma_R(H_s)}\right), \quad (16)$$

where $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the standard normal cumulative distribution function.

To evaluate safe operation when both pitch and heave must remain within their limits, we assume independence of their prediction errors. The joint survival probability is then

$$P_{\text{joint}}(H_s) = P_{\text{pitch safe}}(H_s) \cdot P_{\text{heave safe}}(H_s). \quad (17)$$

The 90% joint survivability limit $H_{s,0.90}$ is defined at each heading as the smallest wave height where

$$P_{\text{joint}}(H_{s,0.90}) = 0.90. \quad (18)$$

This condition yields the dashed black line in the survivability polar plot. The area between the mean envelope and the dashed line is shaded to show the margin lost when demanding 90% confidence across both DOFs.

4.3. Deep Kernel Learning Models

The Pitch polar plot (top-right subplot of Fig 7.) shows the black solid line representing the ground-truth limit state intersecting with the mean predictions from the DKL model denoted by the solid orange line. Regions where the black line is closer to the center than the orange line represents a dangerous situation and highlights why using a stochastic model can help with safe operations. Without an uncertainty metric, using the mean prediction from the model and venturing to the predicted limit state would result in sailing past the actual operational limit for Pitch and potentially damaging the vessel.

Leveraging the stochastic aspect of the Deep Kernel Learning allows for the creation of a 90% survivability line, denoted by the black-dashed line with the shaded blue as the one-sided 90% confidence bounds. If the route planner uses this metric as its operational limits instead of the mean predictions, it would maintain safe operations (exception is small region at ~ 30 degrees).

The lower subplot of Fig 7. highlights which degree of freedom is predicted to trigger the operational limit with its respective color. At that location, the joint one-sided probability of failure for each degree of freedom is taken into account and used for plotting, which is why the uncertainty bands appear different to the individual polar plot uncertainty bands.

As shown in the previous section, after being exposed to 750 shots the base model becomes overconfident in its prediction of large waves. This is demonstrated in the polar plots and the operational envelope in Fig 7. collapsing in locations such as 270 degrees in Pitch. This location shows that the actual pitch limit occurs at a significant wave height of several meters larger. Despite this inaccuracy in limit-state prediction, the uncertainty band in this location is very narrow.

5. Conclusions

This study introduced a probabilistic learning framework that combines a neural network feature extractor with a Gaussian process to predict vessel motion responses while quantifying predictive uncertainty. The resulting distributions were translated into task-specific operational limits, which were then combined into a joint survivability metric. This process enabled the construction of a ninety percent survivability contour that defines a conservative operational envelope for safe route planning.

Results indicate that training on routine seas provides accurate predictions within domain. However, limited fine-tuning of training extreme conditions improves extrapolation but may also reduce uncertainty to overconfident levels in some cases. These findings highlight the importance of calibrated uncertainty for risk-informed decision making and the need to guard against overconfidence when operating in rare or hazardous environments.

The framework offers practical advantages for autonomy assurance and mission planning. Operational envelopes derived from survivability contours can be integrated directly into route planners, adapted as experience accumulates, and used to identify which motion constraints dominate safety across headings and sea states. This provides a principled basis for defining and updating operational limits for autonomous surface vessels.

5.1. Future Work

Future plans include adding slamming frequency as an envelope condition. This provides an added challenge for training because these conditions will not appear in the first routine weather dataset.

Two additional scaling mechanisms are planned to be introduced to address critical shortcomings of purely data-driven approaches. The first uses Mahalanobis distance in feature space to inflate uncertainty in out-of-distribution sea states, preventing overconfidence in extreme or rare conditions. The second incorporates post-mission damage knowledge to locally increase uncertainty near hazardous operating points, thereby embedding human-informed safety factors into the model outputs.

5.2. Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Dr. Jessica Dibelka, ONR code 331 for supporting work to date under grant Number: N00014-20-1-2044

Figure 7.: The model trained with 750 shots of large wave data becomes overconfident in extreme conditions. This can lead to the vessel venturing into conditions past actual safety limits.

References

- [1] N. Clemett, and M. Collette. *Meta-Learning Operational Envelopes for Autonomous Surface Vessels*. Ocean Engineering. In preparation. 2025.
- [2] M. Schirmann, J. Gose and M. Collette. *A Comparison of Physics-Informed Data-Driven Modeling Architectures for Ship Motion Predictions*. Ocean Engineering, Vol. 286. 2023.
- [3] European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts. Data accessed via <https://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/licences/general/>. May 2023.
- [4] ProteusDS. URL: <https://proteusds.com/>.
- [5] Program Executive Office Unmanned and Small Combatants. *U.S. Navy Announces Launch of Vanguard Unmanned Surface Vessel*. 2024.
- [6] A. Cetin, V.R. Solum, and C.M. Evans. *Machine Learning Based Prediction of Wave-Induced Vessel Response*. Ocean Engineering, Vol. 5A, V05AT06A034. 2022.
- [7] M. Collette, R. Bielski, P. Roher, A. Magistro, B. Sulkowski, and J. Van Houten. *Needs Exploration for Long-Term Autonomous Marine Systems: Working Report*. 2022.
- [8] M. Eckstein. *Sea Hunter Unmanned Ship Continues Autonomy Testing as NAVSEA Moves Forward with Draft RFP*. USNI News. 2019.
- [9] K.E. Fjørtoft, and J. Rødseth. *Using the Operational Envelope to Make Autonomous Ships Safer*. 30th European Safety and Reliability Conference and 15th Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Management Conference, Research Publishing Services. pp. 76–83. 2020.
- [10] J. Hensman, A. Matthews, and Z. Ghahramani. *Scalable Variational Gaussian Process Classification*. Proceedings of the Eighteenth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics, PMLR. pp. 351–360. 2015.
- [11] K. Quatch. *IBM's autonomous Mayflower ship breaks down in second transatlantic attempt*. The Register. 2022.
- [12] V. Page, C. Dadswell, M. Webster, M. Jump, and M. Fisher. *Towards the Determination of Safe Operating Envelopes for Autonomous UAS in Offshore Inspection Missions*. Robotics 10(3). 2021.
- [13] T. Petranovic, A. Mikulic, M. Katalinic, M. Corak, and J. Parunov. *Method for Prediction of Extreme Wave Loads Based on Ship Operability Analysis Using Hindcast Wave Database*. Journal of Marine Science and Engineering 9, 1002. 2021.
- [14] J. Rødseth, L.A. Lien Wennersberg, and H. Nordahl. *Towards approval of autonomous ship systems by their operational envelope*. Journal of Marine Science and Technology 27, 67–76. 2022.
- [15] P. Tighineanu, L. Grossberger, P. Baireuther, K. Skubch, S. Falkner, J. Vinogradska, and F. Berkenkamp. *Scalable Meta-Learning with Gaussian Processes*.
- [16] A.G. Wilson, Z. Hu, R. Salakhutdinov, and E.P. Xing. *Deep Kernel Learning*. 2015.
- [17] G. Ziezulewicz. *The littoral combat ship's latest problem: Class-wide structural defects leading to hull cracks*. Navy Times. 2022.